

Using Video Subtitles and the Reading Competence in World Literature of Grade 10 Students

Marlene C. Roxas¹, Cecilia Q. Velasco²

¹Tayabas Western Academy

²Laguna State Polytechnic University

ABSTRACT: Reading competence refers to the comprehending, using, thinking about and engaging with written texts to help the students gain and develop knowledge and skills. The purpose of this study was to find out the effectiveness of using video subtitles in improving reading competence when teaching selections from world literature compared to one of the conventional ways of teaching literature, utilizing read aloud through guided reading approach and with the use of handouts. Results revealed that the null hypotheses among the pre-tests and post-test of control group, pre-test and posttest of the experimental groups, pre-tests of control experimental groups, and also its posttest being compared are not rejected but not fully accepted. The strategies are not fully effective in improving all areas the reading competence. Thus, the hypothesis is supported. Results show that there is a significant difference in the posttest scores of the following reading competencies, sequencing events and answering direct recall questions of the control and experimental groups. Meanwhile, there is no significant difference in the posttest scores of the control and experimental groups based from the results shown in identifying main idea and key details, making inference/predictions, and identifying unfamiliar vocabulary. Therefore, it is concluded that the said strategies are not fully effective in improving all areas of reading competence.

KEYWORDS: competence, experimental, literature, reading, subtitles

INTRODUCTION

Reading competence, as defined by the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA), an international assessment of the basic skills and knowledge in reading, mathematics, and science, refers to the comprehending, using, thinking about and engaging with written texts to be able to attain the universal goals for the students to gain and develop knowledge and skills and also take part in the society. Reading competence includes the mastery of phonics, reading fluency, vocabulary building and enhancement, and reading comprehension. Reading competence can be generalized as having the ability to understand what was read as reading comprehension, being the most substantial reading skills, is a vital component in developing reading skills along with phonological awareness, phonics, fluency, and vocabulary. Having the competency in reading means fully engaging with the text and perceiving what the text wants to imply literally and between the lines. Without this vital competence, a reader will not be provided with any information from what he reads. A person, in overall aspect of living, might be having difficulties with daily activities if reading comprehension ability is not well-developed and practiced. In all, reading competence is indispensable in accessing knowledge. It is an essential and practical capability needed not only in terms of academics, but also in personal and community engagements.

But, in today's world, various reading difficulties and factors are arising contributing to the deficits in reading competence. For example, there are reading comprehension problems encountered by the students due to complexity of text, anxiety, and word recognition (Abeeleh, Al-Ghazo, & Al-Sobh, 2021).[1] Having low reading skills has been one of the major factors in reading comprehension difficulties as identified and showed a study (Satriana, 2018).[2] In addition, reading comprehension difficulties are mainly due to the reason that they hardly identify the main idea of the text, make inference, understand vocabulary, grammar rules, and sentence construction, and little knowledge on the key comprehension strategies (Hidayati, 2018).[3] Meanwhile, it was also discovered that students had reading comprehension problem because they did not know the meaning of the words in the reading materials or text. This is similar with the idea that vocabulary knowledge is also one factor to the comprehension of the students.

To delve with the arising issues and problems with reading competence, different plans of action or schemes such as the key comprehension strategies were developed, enhanced, and utilized; using prior knowledge/ previewing, predicting, identifying the main idea and summarization, questioning, making inferences, visualizing, retelling, and answering comprehension questions strategies (Comprehension: Goal of Reading, 2022).[4] With emphasis on visualizing strategy, students can certainly comprehend texts when they visualize while reading. Viewing is now considered as a major skill and in this globally high technology world, it

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cannot be denied that students' interest in learning is mostly caught when dealing with multimodal texts. In connection to reading, students are able to remember important details from the text when viewing or visualizing.

With the main aim of this research, that is, to help discover essential knowledge in developing and improving students' reading competence, the use of video subtitles in understanding selected narrative texts from world literature and its effects on the reading competence of the students was studied. Multimodal texts, a combination of texts, videos, and images, enhance the opportunity of the students to learn. With this, using video with subtitles in teaching world literature is believed to help improve reading competence.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

With the main aim of this research, that is, to help discover essential knowledge in developing and improving students' reading competence, the use of video subtitles in understanding selected narrative texts from world literature and its effects on the reading competence of the students was studied. Multimodal texts, a combination of texts, videos, and images, enhance the opportunity of the students to learn. With this, using video with subtitles in teaching world literature is believed to help improve reading competence.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

In this study, the researcher used the quasi-experimental research. Quasi-experimental research is concerned with the cause-and-effect relationships between the independent and dependent variables. This design involves the manipulation of the independent variables and the measurements of the dependent variables. In this study, there were experimental and control groups.

Sampling Technique

The participants of the study were the selected Grade 10 students from Tayabas Western Academy located in Candelaria, Quezon. Sixty (60) Grade 10 students were divided into two groups named as experimental and control groups. There were thirty (30) students who belonged to the experimental group and another thirty (30) students under the control group. The participants of the study were identified through the cluster sampling. Cluster sampling is a probability sampling technique where a certain population is divided into groups known as clusters. In this study, the population of Grade 10 students from Tayabas Western Academy were grouped or clustered through the sections. After identifying the sections from Grade 10, the researcher selected two groups from the clusters through simple random sampling technique and labelled as the experimental and control groups of the study.

Research Instruments

The data in this study were gathered by administering pre-test and post-test to the experimental and control groups before and after the conduct of the instruction to determine the effects of using subtitles in the reading competence of the students: identifying main idea and key details, sequencing a passage into an ordinal series, answering direct recall questions, making inference and/or predictions, and identifying unfamiliar vocabulary. The researcher prepared the learning plans, videos with subtitles, reading materials, and the pre and post tests before the conduct of the study.

The researcher constructed a pre-test and post-test which covered the three selections from world literature and were aligned to the reading competencies such as the ability to identify main idea and key details (9 items), ability to sequence a passage into an ordinal series (9 items), ability to answer direct recall questions (9 items), ability to make inference and/or predictions (9 items), and ability to identify unfamiliar vocabulary (9 items). Each test had 45 items in total.

Before the beginning of the instruction, the researcher administered a prepared pre-test to the students. After that, based on the learning plans prepared beforehand, the researcher taught the experimental and control groups. After all the instructions on the selected stories, *The Last Leaf* by O. Henry, *Don Quixote* by Miguel de Cervantes, and *The Necklace* by Guy de Maupassant, the researcher administered the post-test.

Based from the background of research, the researcher applied video subtitles, as the independent variable of the study, in teaching selected narrative texts from world literature to the experimental group consisting of 30 students. Meanwhile, the control group composing of 30 students underwent the reading aloud/guided reading approach of teaching narrative texts from world literature.

Research Procedures

In the conduct of research, the researcher prepared all the needed materials for research such as the manuscript, the videos with subtitles, learning plans, and the pre-test and post-test. The learning plans, videos with subtitles, and the pre-test and post-test were all about some selected texts from world literature such as *The Last Leaf* by O. Henry, *Don Quixote* by Miguel de Cervantes, and *The Necklace* by Guy de Maupassant. These were submitted to the adviser and panel members for research proposal.

Upon approval, the researcher asked permission from the principal of Tayabas Western Academy in Candelaria, Quezon to allow the researcher to conduct a three week-study on the participants by submitting the proper documents and letter of request.

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After sending letters of request and approval by the head of the Junior High School Department of Tayabas Western Academy, the researcher started conducting the study. Pre-test was first administered to the experimental and control group by the researcher. After that, the instruction began.

During the separate instructions for the experimental and control groups, the researcher always began with the sharing of the learning targets to be achieved by the respondents. Preliminary and vocabulary building activities related to the selections were then actively done by the students in the beginning of the class after reading the targets for the day. After the implementation of the initial activities, the researcher proceeded with the introduction of the authors of the selected selections from world literature. The stories selected were *The Last Leaf* by O. Henry, *Don Quixote* by Miguel de Cervantes, and *The Necklace* by Guy de Maupassant.

After the initial activities and introduction of the authors, the application of the interventions began. For the experimental group, the researcher let the respondents watch the videos containing subtitles of the selected stories. Without any distractions, the researcher let the respondents finished watching the whole story. After the viewing activity, the oral discussion of the stories began. Question and answer portion were undergone by the respondents and the researcher. The literal, inferential, and critical comprehensions of the respondents were checked by the researcher through different questions given orally in the class. Important information like the main ideas and key details were identified. Meanwhile, in the control group, after the initial activities and introduction of the authors, reading of the stories aloud came next. The researcher assigned respondents from the control group to read each part of the stories. The researcher applied Guided Reading Approach (GRA) by letting the respondents read the stories in chunks and guiding them while reading by formulating questions at diverse levels in every part of the story to understand the it and check comprehension of the text.

After the discussions, written activities were given. The activities involved answering direct recall questions, sequencing events, and making inferences or predictions.

Finally, the researcher administered post-test to the respondents of the study to gather the final data needed for the study. After the data were gathered, they were submitted to the statistician for the statistical treatment.

Statistical Treatment of Data

To determine the mean score, formula for getting the average was required. Meanwhile, to measure the mean percentage score, its corresponding formula was necessary. Data were statistically treated. To test the significance of the difference between the results derived from the experimental and control groups, the t-test was used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Part I: Mean Pre-Test and Post-test Scores and Standard Deviation of Reading Competencies

Table 1. Mean Pre-Test Scores of the Control Group in Reading Competence Before Applying Read Aloud Through Guided Reading Approach

Reading Competency	M	MPS	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Identify Main Idea and Key Details	3.70	41.11	1.56	Low Proficient
Sequence Events	2.53	28.11	1.22	Low Proficient
Answer Direct Recall Questions	5.90	65.56	1.67	Nearly Proficient
Make Inference/ Predictions	4.17	46.33	1.84	Low Proficient
Identify Unfamiliar Vocabulary	3.47	38.56	1.78	Low Proficient

Note: Legend (MPS): 90-100 – Highly Proficient, 75-89 – Proficient, 50-74 – Nearly Proficient, 25-49 – Low Proficient, 0-24 – Not Proficient

The results show that the respondents in the control group are low proficient in identifying the main idea and key details of selections. This means that the respondents do not yet fully achieve the minimum level of skill in identifying the key concepts in a selection and the important information that support the main idea. The respondents still need further practice to fully understand what the whole text is all about since determining the features of a passage like the main idea and key details are significant to help the students improve their reading comprehension.

In addition, sequencing events is a key comprehension strategy for narrative texts. In this study, it was found out that the respondents in the control group are described to be low proficient in this skill. This means that they have the ability to perceive the happenings in the story but still have the difficulty to organize ideas and identify the logical story structure. The results imply that a focus on various strategies that help students develop their skill in identifying the logical sequence of events should be applied and implemented by the teachers. As per the article of Reading Rockets, differentiated instructions such as scaffolding instruction and use of textual aids like story maps and pictures are some strategies that can be done for efficient organization of information and ideas.

Meanwhile, Table 1 presents the respondents as having low proficiency in making inferences or predictions also. Respondents are having hard time to identify what the text imply. The difficulty in reading between the lines and looking for important information

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indirectly stated is present among the students. Inferences help students decipher and draw conclusions from the information stated in the text to be able to identify the whole meaning of the selections. Based on the mean percentage score and low level of proficiency of the respondents in making inferences or predictions, it conveys to teachers to let the students be aware of and evaluate own thinking by internalizing what the questions are. Reading Rockets (2023)[5] provide essential strategies in teaching how to make inferences and therefore improve reading comprehension such as building knowledge, setting important purposes for reading, and planning many inferential questions to be given to the students.

Furthermore, Table 1 shows also the low proficiency level of the respondents in identifying unfamiliar vocabulary. This conveys low exposure to words and difficulty to apply context clues to decipher the meanings of words. With low vocabulary skills, students' ability to comprehend text may be hindered due to unknown definitions of words in the selections or low skill in getting the context clues and meanings and arriving at a certain definition of the unfamiliar vocabulary.

Among the five reading competencies, it can be seen from the results that the respondents, in terms of answering direct recall questions, are nearly proficient. Looking at the variable with the highest mean score and mean percentage score, the results indicate that the respondents have the minimum level of skill in answering direct recall questions and remembering specific facts from the texts. The respondents know how to key the specific information that are needed to be remembered from the selection.

Table 2. Mean Pre-Test Scores of the Experimental Group in Reading Competence Before Applying Video with Subtitles

Reading Competency	M	MPS	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Identify Main Idea and Key Details	4.00	44.44	1.51	Low Proficient
Sequence Events	3.17	35.22	1.53	Low Proficient
Answer Direct Recall Questions	4.73	52.56	1.44	Nearly Proficient
Make Inference/ Predictions	3.17	35.22	1.62	Low Proficient
Identify Unfamiliar Vocabulary	4.13	45.89	1.33	Low Proficient

Note: Legend (MPS): 90-100 – Highly Proficient, 75-89 – Proficient, 50-74 – Nearly Proficient, 25-49 – Low Proficient, 0-24 – Not Proficient

Table 2 shows that the respondents in the experimental group are low proficient in identifying the main idea and key details, sequencing events, making inferences or predictions, and identifying unfamiliar vocabulary. The level of proficiency that the respondents have indicates that there is a need for improvement in those skills. Having low proficiency in the particular reading competencies also implies that the respondents do not achieve the minimum level of skill they must at least have. Based from the mean percentage scores and level of proficiency, the respondents have difficulty in determining the key concepts and supporting details from selections. The respondents from the experimental group also experienced difficulty in identifying the order of events or sequencing them logically based from the structure of events. In addition, getting information not directly stated from the texts or making inferences seemed to be difficult for the respondents, wherein, with the inability or difficulty to form it, the message of the story conveyed won't be opened and the main purpose of the text will be hardly regarded that is why this should be developed also. Moreover, mean percentage scores for identifying unfamiliar vocabulary indicates that the respondents are low proficient also. This shows that the respondents have trouble with identifying the context clues that may lead them to the meaning of the words and also trouble in reading. In all of these implications of the results, effective strategies in identifying main ideas and key details should be implemented, more practices related to sequencing events must be administered since it is an initial activity for more sophisticated ways of understanding the structure or components of narrative text and more inferential questions and vocabulary activities should be given to the students for the overall improvement of the reading competence of the students.

Table 2 also shows the level of proficiency of the respondents when it comes to answering direct recall questions. The respondents are nearly proficient. They can remember important facts and details from stories and thus recall it when direct questions are given to them. Since these questions are answerable by details directly stated from the selections, respondents can easily just recall from their memory the important facts and state it. The result implies that students are able to decode text as well as comprehend and remember the stated details from the selection (Robb, 2015). [6] This is a good sign that another set of students can be expected to perform well in future exams since the skill for active recall is present (Owen, 2022).[7]

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Table 3. Mean Post-test Scores of the Control Group in Reading Competence After Applying Read Aloud Through Guided Reading Approach

Reading Competency	M	MPS	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Identify Main Idea and Key Details	5.53	61.44	1.81	Nearly Proficient
Sequence Events	5.50	61.11	1.61	Nearly Proficient
Answer Direct Recall Questions	6.97	77.44	2.16	Proficient
Make Inference/ Predictions	5.77	64.11	1.99	Nearly Proficient
Identify Unfamiliar Vocabulary	4.13	45.89	1.53	Low Proficient

Note: Legend (MPS): 90-100 – Highly Proficient, 75-89 – Proficient, 50-74 – Nearly Proficient, 25-49 – Low Proficient, 0-24 – Not Proficient

Results show that the respondents, in terms of answering direct recall questions, are proficient or skilled. It can be seen from the results that the students' performance in answering direct recall questions shows a high result in the mean score, mean percentage score, and most especially in proficiency level. This indicates that among the five reading competencies, students under the control group truly excel in answering the direct recall questions commonly starting with who, what, when, where. Students are skilled at retaining important details directly stated from the texts with reading aloud of the story through guided reading approach and with the use of handouts. It can also be concluded that one of the reasons why students easily comprehend the text and remember details is because the students make reading personal mainly based from their prior knowledge and texts. They have read the printed copy and read it aloud in the class. The results gathered show also that students were able to have long-term retention.

Meanwhile, the respondents are nearly proficient in skills such as identifying main idea and key details, sequencing events, and making inferences/predictions. This means that they have the minimum skill level of the said competencies. Respondents from the control group were able to get what the whole text is all about and determine the supporting details to the main idea. Respondents were able to locate major and minor information from the text. On the other hand, the respondents possess the ability to sequence events in a logical manner. Respondents were able to identify the components of a selection such as the beginning, middle, and ending. This ability is a good foundation for more sophisticated ways of understanding the structure or components of narrative text. While, it was also found out that the respondents can make inferences/predictions. Respondents from the control group were able to use their thinking and imagination and connect ideas and details in the text to arrive at a certain implied information or conclusion. This conveys that the respondents can read between the lines.

Table 3 also shows that, after the application of the strategy, the skill of the respondents from the control group in identifying unfamiliar vocabulary got the lowest proficiency level. Respondents are low proficient in determining the meaning of the particular words used from the selections. Respondents cannot fully correctly recognize words based on how they were used inside the stories. With this low skill in vocabulary, readers may lose the whole meaning of the passage (Ascend Learning Center, 2019).[8] While reading aloud helps in vocabulary building as found out in the study of Daud, Kazi, and Kalsoom (2019),[9] this present study concluded from this result that while and after applying the strategy of reading aloud using handouts and while doing the guided reading approach, the respondents were not able to successfully find the meaning of the vocabulary. This can be due to the complexity of the word, inability to use context clues efficiently, and more focus given to the important details and happenings in the stories read.

To sum it up, respondents from the control group really were able to use their thinking and imagination and connect ideas and details in the text to arrive at a certain implied information or conclusion. This conveys that the respondents can read between the lines which is far better than unable to use context clues efficiently.

Table 4. Mean Post-test Scores of the Experimental Group in Reading Competence After Applying Video with Subtitles

Reading Competency	M	MPS	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Identify Main Idea and Key Details	6.10	67.78	1.88	Nearly Proficient
Sequence Events	6.53	72.56	1.87	Nearly Proficient
Answer Direct Recall Questions	8.27	91.89	0.98	Highly Proficient
Make Inference/ Predictions	6.50	72.22	1.93	Nearly Proficient
Identify Unfamiliar Vocabulary	4.60	51.11	1.69	Nearly Proficient

Note: Legend (MPS): 90-100 – Highly Proficient, 75-89 – Proficient, 50-74 – Nearly Proficient, 25-49 – Low Proficient, 0-24 – Not Proficient

This table highly presents the remarkable results based from the mean scores and mean percentage scores of the different variables after applying video with subtitles in teaching selections from world literature. The students from the experimental group

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achieved high proficiency level in answering direct recall questions. This means that the respondents were highly capable of recalling specific facts stated from the texts and answering correctly the direct recall questions given.

The noticeable result gained from answering direct recall questions indicates that the students from the experimental group truly performed well. Students are good at retaining important details directly stated from the texts. One factor that can be considered in attaining the highest proficiency in answering direct recall questions among all the reading competencies and in comparison to the results of the mean percentage scores of the control group is that while the students were watching the video, aside from the visual representations and what they heard from the video, they were able to retain it more since they read subtitles on the bottom part of the screen containing the important details directly stated from the story. The results also indicate that the students have a firm foundation for the advanced level of reading comprehension since they are highly proficient in answering direct recall questions or determining significant information from which literary comprehension focuses on (Santo Domingo, 2020).[10] In addition, Nurjanah and Putri (2022)[11] revealed in their study; that good and very good mastery of literal comprehension leads to the understanding of text based from the inferential and evaluative or critical levels.

Meanwhile, the post-test of the respondents in identifying main idea and key details, sequencing events, making inferences/predictions, and identifying unfamiliar vocabulary resulted to near proficiency level. The same with the results, after utilizing read aloud strategy through guided reading approach with the use of handouts, in identifying main idea and key details, sequencing events, making inferences/predictions, the respondents from the experimental group were able to discover the key concepts of the text and determine the supporting details to the main idea. Respondents were able to identify the topic of the passages and recognize the major and minor information. Also, respondents were able to remember the happenings in the stories chronologically that helps them to answer specific questions related to sequencing events. With this ability of the respondents, students can have various opportunities to examine the whole text and narrative components. Furthermore, respondents can make inferences based from the given information in the text. They were able to arrive at conclusions based on their evaluation of the situations in the text. Moreover, respondents were able to identify meaning of the particular words used from the selections. Respondents can correctly recognize words based on how they were used inside the stories. The application of video subtitles in the instruction helped improved the mean the percentage score of the respondents in identifying vocabulary. This is supported by a study authored by Sadiku (2017)[12] where, after the conduct and further statistical analysis, it was found out that using video subtitles is indeed a great tool in developing student's vocabulary.

Thus, the students from the experimental group truly performed well in answering direct recall questions. Students are good at retaining important details directly stated from the texts. They were also able to correctly recognize words based on how they were used inside the stories. They were able to retain it more since they read subtitles on the bottom part of the screen containing the important details directly stated.

Table 5. Overall Performance of the Respondents Based on the Mean Percentage Scores (MPS) Before and After the Treatments

Group	Overall Performance			
	Mean Percentage Score	Interpretation Pre-Test	Mean Percentage Score	Interpretation Posttest
	Pre-Test		Posttest	
Experimental	42.67%	Low Proficient	71.11%	Nearly Proficient
Control	43.93%	Low Proficient	62.00%	Nearly Proficient

Note: Legend (MPS): 90-100 – Highly Proficient, 75-89 – Proficient, 50-74 – Nearly Proficient, 25-49 – Low Proficient, 0-24 – Not Proficient

It can be seen from the results that in the pre-test, the experimental and control group has only a difference of 1.26% where the control got the higher MPS. This implies that the respondents from the control group scored higher than the experimental group. Meanwhile, after the application of the two strategies in the instructions, read aloud through guided reading approach with the use of handouts and video subtitles, higher MPS results on the post-tests for the control and experimental group were shown on Table 5. The table presents that an increase in the mean percentage scores of the experimental group from pre-test to post-test, the same with the control group. The reading skills of the respondents are nearly proficient. This means that after the application of the strategies, the respondents had achieved the acceptable minimum skill level in reading. Meanwhile, the MPS of each group in the post-test highly differs with 9.11% difference. This shows that the use of video subtitles in teaching selections from world literature is more effective in improving the mean percentage scores of the respondents.

Table 6. Significant Difference Between the Pre-Test and Post-test Scores of the Control Group

Variables	Pre-Test Control		Posttest - Control		T	Df	Sig. (2-Tailed)	Interpretation
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation				
Identifying Main Idea and Key Details	3.70	1.56	5.53	1.81	-4.634	29	0.000	Significant
Sequencing Events	2.53	1.22	5.50	1.61	-8.796	29	0.000	Significant
Answering Direct Recall Questions	5.90	1.67	6.97	2.16	-1.937	29	0.063	Not Significant
Making Inference/Predictions	4.17	2.16	5.77	1.99	-3.247	29	0.003	Significant
Identifying Unfamiliar Vocabulary	3.47	1.78	4.13	1.53	-1.658	29	0.108	Not Significant

Note: Legend: Sig (2-tailed) ≤ 0.05 (Significant), Sig (2-tailed) ≥ 0.05 (Not significant)

Results show that there is a significant difference in the pre-test and post-test scores of the following reading competencies, identifying main idea and key details, sequencing events, and making inference/predictions, thus the utilization of read aloud strategy executed with the guided reading approach and using of handouts in teaching world literature is effective in those competencies. It can be inferred also that with the intensive exposure to the written text from the handouts and having the time to read the story carefully, students were able to identify carefully the main idea and key details, know the sequence of events, and read between the lines or make inferences/predictions that are not directly stated from the text. A study by Hazzard (2016) [13] entitled “The Effects of Read Alouds on Student Comprehension” support this conclusion as it was found out that student comprehension scores got higher after applying read aloud and gathering data through observations, interviews, questionnaires, and comprehension questions.

Meanwhile, there is no significant difference in the pre-test and post-test scores of the control group based from the results shown in answering direct recall questions and identifying unfamiliar vocabulary – not significant. This implies that the utilization of read aloud through guided reading approach with the use of handouts is not seen to be effective in improving the ability of the students to recognize and remember significant information and identify word meanings. From this finding, comparing to the other competencies which tend to be more improved when implementing the strategy, it can be deduced that while the strategy seems to be effective at looking for the main idea, key details, order of events, and inferences or predictions, students were seen to be not pushed through higher level of improvements when it comes to remembering and recalling information identify word meanings. This may be due to some factors like having the attention on knowing more about the whole meaning of the text and not giving proper emphasis also on the details directly stated from the story and more attention in understanding more the meaning of words through context clues.

Based from the findings presented on Table 6, the read aloud strategy done through guided reading approach has been beneficial in varied ways. The application of the said strategy during the instructions had helped students improved their different skills in reading. Student’s active listening and working memory are enhanced (Anderson, 2022).[14] With the read aloud strategy, everyone in class can be engaged to the story read while listening to the reader and having intensive exposure to the written copies of the selections called handouts. In fact, according to a study by Acosta-Tello (2019),[15] while students are dealing with reading competencies such as making inferences and connections with the character, students are more engaged. Better engagement with the selections results to great experience and greater development in language and reading. Also, with the use of guided reading approach, students are guided on each part of the stories and led to know where emphasis on important happenings in the selections should be given. This conventional way of teaching literature has been an efficient strategy that can be applied inside the classroom. Student and teacher interactions are present and a more detailed discussions of the story is done.

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Table 7. Significant Difference Between the Pre-Test and Post-test Scores of the Experimental Group

Variables	Pre-Test Experimental		Posttest Experimental		T	Df	Sig. (2-Tailed)	Interpretation
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation				
Identifying Main Idea and Key Details	4.00	1.51	6.10	1.88	-4.92	29	0.000	Significant
Sequencing Events	4.00	1.51	6.53	1.87	-5.52	29	0.000	Significant
Answering Direct Recall Questions	4.73	1.44	8.27	0.98	-9.87	29	0.000	Significant
Making Inference/Predictions	3.17	1.62	6.50	1.93	-6.34	29	0.000	Significant
Identifying Unfamiliar Vocabulary	4.13	1.33	4.60	1.69	-1.05	29	0.305	Not Significant

Note: Legend: Sig (2-tailed) ≤ 0.05 (Significant), Sig (2-tailed) ≥ 0.05 (Not significant)

The significant difference on the following reading competencies: identifying main idea and key details, sequencing events, answering direct recall questions, and making inference/predictions, derived from the gathered data means that the use of video subtitles in teaching selections in world literature is effective. This conclusion can be supported by a study authored by Supangesti, Sutapa, and Salam (2018)[16] where it was discovered that reading comprehension was improved with use of video subtitles based from the scores gained. Furthermore, based from the statistical interpretation, it can be inferred that having the subtitles aside from the video itself showing visual representations like animations help improve the students' comprehension of the selections. The respondents could easily identify what the whole story was all about because aside from the images, audio, and videos, they can read subtitles where they can more easily decode what has been said by the character. This is the same with ability to sequence events and answer direct recall questions. They actually see the happenings from the story like the actions and how the scenarios are set and what they hear, see, and read from the subtitles can be part of their memory for remembering and recalling. While, with subtitles, students were able to create deeper understanding of the whole text and also recognize more the images or visuals from the videos for inferring unstated details.

Meanwhile, there is no significant difference in the pre-test and post-test scores of the experimental group based from the results shown in identifying unfamiliar vocabulary – not significant. This implies that using video subtitles is not seen to be effective in improving the ability of the students to identify word meanings. This can be due to the fact that they were trying to understand the whole selection by going with the flow of the events of the story and due to time constraints that subtitles appeared and disappeared at a specific timestamp. The result of this study is contrary to the study by Sadiku (2017)[17] and previous papers where it was found out that the use of subtitles can be a very great tool for vocabulary acquisition and learning. This finding is parallel to the results gained from the study of Bellalem, et.al. (2018)[18] where subtitled movies as comprehensible inputs in the experiment became effective in vocabulary acquisition.

Table 7 presenting the data gathered from statistical analysis indicates the beneficial impacts of using video subtitles in teaching selected texts from world literature. It has been effective in honing almost all of the reading competencies. Subtitles, in addition to the visual representations and audio that the video contained, led to more exposure of the students to the selections have been an aid to improved reading comprehension. Student's attentions can be easily caught since they are called as visual learners. Lewis (2022)[19] stated in his article that some of the benefits of subtitles are development of language skills and enjoyment.

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Table 8. Significant Difference Between the Pre-Test Scores of The Control and Experimental Groups

Pretest Scores		M	SD	t	df	Sig. (2-Tailed)	Interpretation
Identify Main Idea and Key Details	Control	3.70	1.56	-0.758	58	0.452	Not Significant
	Experimental	4.00	1.51				
Sequence Events	Control	2.53	1.22	-1.768	58	0.082	Not Significant
	Experimental	3.17	1.53				
Answer Direct Recall Questions	Control	5.90	1.67	2.902	58	0.005	Significant
	Experimental	4.73	1.44				
Make Inference/ Predictions	Control	4.17	1.84	2.234	58	0.029	Significant
	Experimental	3.17	1.62				
Identify Unfamiliar Vocabulary	Control	3.47	1.78	-1.645	58	0.105	Not Significant
	Experimental	4.13	1.33				

Note: Legend: Sig (2-tailed) \leq 0.05 (Significant), Sig (2-tailed) \geq 0.05 (Not significant)

Based from the results shown on Table 8, it was shown that pre-test scores are significant and not significant for some variables presented. There is no significant difference in the pre-test scores of the control and experimental groups in the skills identifying main idea and key details, sequencing events, and identifying unfamiliar vocabulary while there is a significant difference in the pre-test scores of the following reading competencies before the application of the strategies, answering direct recall questions and making inference/predictions. The different results on the significance and non-significance of the pre-test scores indicate that the two groups have differences before the interventions took place.

Table 9. Significant Difference Between the Post-test Scores of the Control and Experimental Groups

Posttest scores		M	SD	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Interpretation
Identify Main Idea and Key Details	Control	5.53	1.81	-1.187	58	0.240	Not Significant
	Experimental	6.10	1.88				
Sequence Events	Control	5.50	1.61	-2.291	58	0.026	Significant
	Experimental	6.53	1.87				
Answer Direct Recall Questions	Control	6.97	2.16	-3.005	58	0.004	Significant
	Experimental	8.27	0.98				
Make Inference/ Predictions	Control	5.77	1.99	-1.449	58	0.153	Not Significant
	Experimental	6.50	1.93				
Identify Unfamiliar Vocabulary	Control	4.13	1.53	-1.121	58	0.267	Not Significant
	Experimental	4.60	1.69				

Note: Legend: Sig (2-tailed) \leq 0.05 (Significant), Sig (2-tailed) \geq 0.05 (Not significant)

Table 9 presents the significant differences of the reading competencies between the post-test scores of the control and experimental groups after the application of video with subtitles and read aloud through guided reading approach with the use of handouts in teaching selected texts in world literature. Here is the comprehensive verbal interpretation of the table.

In testing the significant difference of the control and experimental groups in identifying main idea and key details in the post-test, table shows that the two groups are statistically not significant since the p-value 0.240 is greater than the standard significance level of 0.05 having the degree of freedom of 58. It is derived based from the mean of the control group, 5.53, and its standard deviation 1.81 and the mean of the experimental group which is 6.10 and a standard deviation of 1.88. These results mainly show that the application of video subtitles in teaching selections from world literature has no significant difference or impact on the post-test scores of the respondents in the experimental group in comparison to the results of the control group. It can be concluded that using video subtitles does not bring noticeable impact in improving the skill of the respondents in determining the key concepts and details.

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While, results from the table show that the post-test for sequencing events of the control group has a mean of 5.50 and a standard deviation of 1.61 while the experimental group has a mean of 6.53 and a standard deviation of 1.87. It can be interpreted that the two groups are statistically significant since the p-value of 0.026 is greater than the 0.05 significance level with 58 as the degree of freedom. There is a significant difference between the post-tests of the two groups. With reference to these stated findings, it can be deduced that when it comes to arranging events chronologically, the use of subtitles is fully effective as it brought impact and improvement on the said reading skill of the respondents.

The interpretation for sequencing events is the same with answering direct recall questions. Results from the table show that the post-test of the control group for answering direct recall questions has a mean of 6.97 and a standard deviation of 2.16 while experimental group has 8.27 as its mean and 0.98 as its standard deviation. It can be interpreted that the post-tests of the two groups are statistically significant since the p-value of 0.004 is less than the 0.05 significance level with 58 as the degree of freedom which means that the use of subtitles is also effective in improving the competency of the respondents to remember and recall specific facts and information stated in the texts. There is a significant difference between the post-tests of the two groups. With subtitles at the bottom of the video, respondents were able to memorize or stick in their mind the major and minor details of the selections.

Meanwhile, Table 9 indicates that the skill of the respondents to make inferences/predictions has not been largely impacted or improved with the use of video subtitles. The post-tests of the experimental and control groups on making inference/predictions are not significant since the p-value of 0.153 is less than the standard significance level of 0.05 having the degree of freedom of 58. The control's post-test has a mean of 5.77 and standard deviation of 1.99 while the experimental has a mean of 6.50 and a standard deviation of 1.93. There is no significant difference between the post-tests of the two groups. The data conclude that the use of video subtitles is not effective in improving the said skill as it has no significant difference with the post-test of the control group from which the read aloud strategy through guided reading approach with the use of handouts was applied.

Lastly, results from the table show that the post-test of the control group for identifying unfamiliar vocabulary has a mean of 4.13 and a standard deviation of 1.53 while the pre-test of the experimental group has a mean of 4.60 and a standard deviation of 1.69 for post-test. It can be interpreted also from this calculation that the pre-test and post-test are statistically not significant since the p-value of 0.267 is greater than the 0.05 significance level with 58 as the degree of freedom. The implementation of the strategy in the experimental group based from the post-test results shows no significant difference in the use of the strategy in the control group. It can be concluded that using video subtitles does not bring remarkable impact in improving the skill of the respondents in identifying unfamiliar vocabulary.

Based from the results given, it is therefore concluded that the said strategy is not fully effective in improving all areas of reading competence. The use of video subtitles is effective in improving the reading competence of the students in sequencing events and answering direct recall questions but do not give significant impact on identifying the main idea and key details, making inferences, and identifying unfamiliar vocabulary.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

CONCLUSIONS

In light of the above findings, the following conclusions in this study were drawn:

1. Results show that there is a significant difference in the pre-test and post-test scores of the following reading competencies, identifying main idea and key details, sequencing events, and making inference/predictions. Meanwhile, there is no significant difference in the pre-test and post-test scores of the control group based from the results shown in answering direct recall questions and identifying unfamiliar vocabulary. Therefore, it is concluded that the said strategy is not fully effective in improving all areas of reading competence. The null hypothesis is supported.
2. Results show that there is a significant difference in the pre-test and post-test scores of the following reading competencies, identifying main idea and key details, sequencing events, answering direct recall questions, and making inference/predictions. Meanwhile, there is no significant difference in the pre-test and post-test scores of the experimental group based from the results shown in identifying unfamiliar vocabulary. Therefore, it is concluded that the said strategy is not fully effective in improving all areas of reading competence. The null hypothesis is supported.
3. There is no significant difference in the pre-test scores of the control and experimental groups based from the results shown in identifying main idea and key details, sequencing events, and identifying unfamiliar vocabulary. Meanwhile, results show that there is a significant difference in the pre-test scores of the following reading competencies before the application of the strategies, answering direct recall questions and making inference/predictions. The null hypothesis is supported.
4. Results show that there is a significant difference in the post-test scores of the following reading competencies, sequencing events and answering direct recall questions of the control and experimental groups. Meanwhile, there is no significant difference in the post-test scores of the control and experimental groups based from the results shown in identifying main idea and key details, making inference/predictions, and identifying unfamiliar vocabulary. Therefore, it is concluded that the said strategies are not fully effective in improving all areas of reading competence. The null hypothesis is supported.

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RECOMMENDATIONS

After careful analysis of the results of the study, the researcher recommends the following:

1. It can be seen that students improved their skills and performance while dealing with varied strategies and approaches. For the teachers, it is recommended to continue applying varied and interactive strategies and approaches in teaching for effective transfer of learning, skill development, and improved performance of the students.
2. Using video subtitles and read aloud strategy through guided reading approach and with the use of handouts can be applied in varied instructions since both strategies can be effective in honing reading skills. In the application of these, it is recommended to prepare varied activities that will develop more the students' skills in reading.
3. For future researchers, it is recommended to conduct further studies about the use of video subtitles in improving the reading competence of the students. It is also recommended to give emphasis on the influence of the principles of subtitles such as the format, screentime, and access to the students in the reading competence.
4. For future educators, seek for and study other strategies that will be effective in enhancing students' reading competencies in their future researches.

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